

SEMANTIC AND STRUCTURAL FEATURES OF COMPUTER TECHNOLOGY TERMS

Omonova Makhfurat Keldiyarovna

PHD (Karshi SU)

Mukiddinova Maftuna Nuriddinovna

Master (Karshi SU)

Abstract: The swift advancement of contemporary technologies has led to a rise in the number of new terms in our native language. The lexicon of the Uzbek language is regularly getting rich at the expense of internal and external sources. Throughout the 19th and 20th centuries, the process of assimilation and disuse of words accelerated. The terms have several distinct origins. They are formed by taking words from another language, making a new word based on the existing vocabulary and grammatical rules of the language or making a new meaning out of one of a word's dictionary definitions.

Key words: terminology, terms, computer technologies, borrowed words, Information Communication Technologies, translation, abbreviation, extra-linguistic, intra-linguistic factors, etymology, assimilation, meaning.

There are different ways of acquiring foreign words in the Uzbek language. In the event that an idea is directly appropriated despite lacking a precise Uzbek term and having a good and useful impact. Borrowed words are also widely used in the field of information technologies. New technical words have emerged in tandem with the introduction of new devices. For a variety of extra-linguistic and intra-linguistic factors, learning other languages is activated in the current stage of Uzbek language development.

"The terminology of each field in a certain field of science or practice is characterized as meaningful and functional with the attachment of specialists to a narrow circle of communication. They are the only ones who can truly comprehend each term's meaning accurately and thoroughly. The terms can only be used most accurately by professionals. Still, specialists' contributions go beyond these specific areas. They not only create terms, but also determine the limits of the content of terms. When there are a number of naming options in front of them, they choose the rightest terminological name for understanding," said Danilenko.¹⁶

Indeed, computer terms are understandable only to those who deal with the field of informatics and more used by them. Due to the development of Information Communication Technologies, these terms are now becoming a more understandable language among ordinary people. But all the same does not understand the original

¹⁶ V.P.Danilenko "Русская терминология" издательство наука, 1977. Page 181

meaning of any term. People can comprehend the meaning without the need for a translation because of the term's function. However, they do not fully understand its origin or original meaning or where does this term come from. Therefore, such researchers as us have the task of developing such terms. The current investigation focuses on abbreviations and examines the etymology of computer terms and terms which assimilated into the Uzbek language from foreign languages in the field of information technologies and the composition of terms which are now used in a wide range of official communications and publications.

If we look at the etymology of computer terms the origin of most of them goes back to the English language as some of them are used in the same word form in other languages without translation. Some are accepted as abbreviations for the Uzbek language. For example, IT is "Information Technology" from the English language which is an abbreviation of the words "axborot texnologiyalari" in Uzbek. Even so, the word is now pronounced and used in the form of IT in colloquial and written speech.

IT-Park – abbreviation of words from the English language "Information Technology".

Meaning: a place where active and talented in the field of IT where people can bring their ideas through accounting, legal, marketing and education which will have a real opportunity to turn into real business projects.

Gif - Graphics Interchange Format (the image sharing format)

Meaning: it can store several images in one file and it is very convenient for simple animations.

Jpeg – abbreviation of the term Joint Photographic Experts Group

Meaning: common type of computer graphics developed by a united group of photography experts, the most extensive one.

Pcx - PC eXchange.

Meaning: sharing information on a personal computer.

Pdf - abbreviation of the term Portable Document Format.

Meaning: at first, it was intended for keeping printed products in electronic form. Currently raster and vector images with text are also stored in it.

SMM - Social Media Marketing.

Meaning: in social media marketing promoting products, goods and services in social networks.

In the practice of creating and organizing terminological systems, the concept of "abbreviation of a term" is widely used. In my opinion, it is a short form of the name although it is stronger in terminological practice, it is not very successful. It is better and more correct to call them as the short form of the term. The short version of a term legalized for use in a terminological standard is convenient and appears through various models of word combinations. Therefore, the introduction of short versions presented

in professional oral communication. Therefore, the introduction of short versions is present in professional oral communication and deliberately it creates more convenient and semantically equivalent names which attract specialists. When dealing with abbreviations, as English abbreviations and extensions are taken in a compatible way, the abbreviations in the Uzbek language are not compatible with each other. Because Abbreviations of Uzbek terms are accepted in English the capital letters of the words without any translations as most of the computer terms are taken directly from the English language without any translation.

Nowadays, compared to other terminological systems, information technology terminology has a higher number of foreign terms and most of them are taken from English. The computer lexicon is so rich that it is insufficient to consider them only in terms of abbreviations. Therefore, I would like to pay special attention to the etymology of words related to the main device of the computer.

In 1954, IBM France tried to find a French translation of the English word "computer". The words "calculateur" or "calculatrice" were not very suitable in the literary translation, because it was used for data processing electronic machine. IBM contacted Jacques Perret, professor of Latin philology at the Sorbonne, to find a good equivalent of the word "computer". In his letter dated April 16, 1955, he proposed the term "computer". But in addition to this term, Jacques Perre proposed such terms as "systemateur", "combinateur", "congesteur" and "synthétiseur". But each of these proposed terms did not match each other at the lexical or grammatical level. Therefore, the term "computer" was the most appropriate in every way and it was accepted as a technical term and even became familiar with everyday vocabulary.

As the birthplace of the computer was England, many computer terms were taken verbatim from the English language. Such terms are often found not only in our daily language, but also in various class textbooks. During my research, I tried to analyze the terms found in the 7th grade "Information and communications technology" textbook. As a result of the analysis, the following terms related to the field of information and communications technologies can be cited.

Messenjer –courier, messenger (eng)

Meaning: a program designed for instant text messages, audio recordings sharing of photos and other multimedia.

Akkaunt – account (eng).

Meaning: personal page or personal cabinet of the user after registering on this site.

Inter – enter (eng).

Meaning; set information.

Multimedya – multimedia (eng).

Meaning: multiple media.

Glossiri – glossary (eng).

Meaning: terms used in a theme.

Modul – module (eng).

Meaning: example, unit.

Shrift – shrift (eng).

Meaning: a character defining the size, shape, color, thickness of the writing.

Kreyt stayl - Create style (eng).

Meaning: box to enter the format settings you want to create.

Stil – style (eng).

Meaning: style, variety.

Modifay – modify (eng).

Meaning: Specify the necessary formats for the text style.

Tekst – text (eng).

Meaning: text.

Farmat – format (eng).

Meaning: create a document type.

Skver – square (eng).

Meaning: border around image, text.

Top en botm –

top and bottom (eng).

Meaning: create a text on the top and bottom of an image.

Edit – edit (eng).

Meaning; edit, rewrite something.

Teybl – table (eng).

Meaning: table of some information or data.

Paragrf – paragraph (eng).

Meaning: passage, set of elements in computer science.

Element – element (eng).

Meaning: an item, a word.

Dokument - Document (eng).

Meaning: document.

Adaptr – adapter (eng)

Meaning: adapter, portable mechanism.¹⁷

Aftor - Author (eng).

Meaning: to set an author's name.

Dokument info - document info (eng.)

Meaning: document which consists of information

¹⁷ Volkovskaya D.L., Pircmqulova A., Hakimov M. Inglizcha-Ruscha-0'zbekcha kompyuter ilmi bo'yicha o'quv lug'ati. Toshkent 2005. Page 5.

Fayl – file (eng).

Meaning: folder where documents are stored.

Dezayn – design (eng).

Meaning: to decorate the appearance of something.

Portret -portrait (eng).

Meaning: image, create an image or a picture.

Conclusion: to summarize, borrowed words appear with the needs of society and time and take on the color of permanence according to their use. It is clear that these analyses represent these words which have their own alternative in our language are also used in an appropriate manner. However, some adopted words have their own alternative in our language. Take the word “trend” as a good example. In our daily life, we can see the word “trend” used in relation to music, clothes or colors. But there is an Uzbek word “ommabop” as an alternative to the word “trend” in Uzbek language. There are many such borrowed words.

a) The number of English borrowed words in the lexicon of the Uzbek language is increasing.

b) Due to the lack of alternative words, they are used without any changes.

c) Some borrowed words are not included in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language.

d) 2 different usage of proper words can cause many spelling errors. Therefore, it is necessary to ensure that they are used only in one sense

It is worth saying that today the English language is increasingly strengthening its position as an international language and it is becoming the language of scientific research. Therefore, the spread of words related to the English language is expanding through global and social networks and scientific sources. Actively used words in English are becoming terminologies. Therefore, it is appropriate to use them correctly and appropriately in the process of assimilation of borrowed words entering the language through various sources, to use borrowed words in texts with limited translation possibilities or in the absence of a national expression that shows the original patterns of appropriation.

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